

USING VERIOUS TEACHING METHODS IN ENGLISH LESSONS

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Annotasiyon: It is important to use new teaching methods in an enthusiastic way and engage the class actively in a discussion about the key topic area. This can be done in a wide variety of ways of using pictures, maps, or personalized questions about the subject matter.

Key words: project, role, teacher, about, positive, negative, new language, students.

It would be better if the teacher create new project for every lesson. The layout of the classroom can be instrumental in creating a positive working atmosphere for project work. In order to work in a small groups, the teacher should rearrange the desks, with a table in the middle, so the students are seating facing to each other. This will facilitate face to face interaction and encourage cooperation. It is often good idea to nominate one student as the group “secretary” to write down notes and assist in focusing the others on the task in hand. The role as a teacher will change and develop according to the stage of the project. In the early stages, you will need to spend time explaining important points to the whole class and clarifying any new language. As the project moves on to the stages where learners are required to create something, teachers role will changed to that of monitor, resource and facilitator. While students are busy working and teacher must circulate around the classroom helping them with vocabulary and useful phrases. Such kind of project work provides many valuable opportunities for students to learn new vocabulary and expressions. The teacher should always encourage his class to start and maintain PVD (professional vocabulary development) notebooks or lists where they write down useful new words that come up. Teacher can support this by writing new

expressions on a special section on the board. At the end of the project teacher always must give his class positive feedback. It is a good idea to have a final stage where students can see the work that others have produced. However sometimes it is difficult to make a project or to conduct a lesson because of problematic groups. Obviously, it is easy to work with an obedient group. A skillful teacher must *ménage* with everything.

Teacher – group conflicts are in many ways the most painful group experience for teachers, who can feel attacked, exposed and hurt that their ideas, teaching style, and methodology have been rejected. Problems of ideology, humiliation, and hurt pride can complicate the situation and get in the way of finding a suitable solution. These situations can end in bitterness and frustration for all concerned. The teacher is responsible for group problems and can solve some of them for example, the conflicts between teacher and students. This, of course, is the aim of the all process, but it is important to get all opinions thoroughly aired first, otherwise resentment will remain and be detrimental to the search for a solution. It is important to establish that everyone has laid all they want to about the problem before beginning to work on a solution , though obviously the debate must be stopped if it begins to go round in circles and repeat itself. To find out if everyone has had their say on the issue, summarize the various (note on the board will help)and ask if anyone has anything new to add.

The process of finding a solution should be a win- win negotiations, not a winlose one: it is important to reach a consensus solution, not a majority vote. For instance teacher should act as an actor and play some gentle music as a background and ask the students to close their eyes and try to visualize a positive outcome to dispute, a solution that would make them feel happy and make the class enjoyable place to be. Ask them to open their eyes and to tell the person sitting next to them about the outcome they visualized. Then ask each pair to tell the group about the vision for the future. This exercise redirects energy from negative feelings to positive ones in order to the ground for a more constructive discussion. Another solution to this problem is using the method “Brainstorming”. If a group has been close and affectionate, it is easy for them to feel them let down, abandoned and lost at the end of a course, when the group life is over and everyone disperses, in this situation it is important to change their position. Furthermore,

teacher should divide the group into pairs and give each pair a pile of small pieces of paper. Set a time- limit for students. They should write down whatever comes into their head, however unlikely or bizarre the suggestion seems.

They shouldn't reject ideas simply because they don't agree with them, write everything down. When the time-limit is up, the teacher should stop them and ask everyone to contribute suggestions. He also must write them all on the board. This exercise is a way of getting group members to think laterally and see the possibilities outside their own point of view. A "group brainstorm" on ways of learning English after the course is over is a useful way of pulling ideas: student will be able to suggest ideas that may not have occurred to others in the group. To sum up I want to say that every teacher should be sometimes serious and strict, sometimes uses jokes and be as a friend but he always must use new teaching methods in each his lessons and projects. It's nice to end the term on a positive note, and give students a chance to express their feelings towards one another.

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